

SUFFIXAL ALLOMORPHES FORMING OBJECT NOUNS IN THE PERSIAN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. The affixation of nouns has a special place in the morphology of the Persian language. This method creates a new word by adding prefixes, infixes, and suffixes to the base. In particular, the creation of a noun by suffixes and its suffixal allomorphs is important in further expanding the vocabulary of the Persian language. Following are the most effective methods of forming object nouns in Persian language: PrTVB + suffixal allomorphs, PTVB + suffixal allomorphs, adjective + suffixal allomorphs, noun + suffixal allomorphs. This article discusses the functional and semantic properties of suffixal allomorphs that make Persian nouns as well as their use in context through examples derived from sources and literary books..

Keywords: PrTVB (present tense verb base), PTVB (past tense verb base), suffix, suffixal allomorph, object noun.

Introduction. In Persian, making object nouns through suffixes is a productive method. In this article, we select some of the infixes that are allomorphic based on the suffixes mentioned in the works of the Russian linguist L.S. Peysikov, "Ocherki po slovoobrazovaniyu persidskogo yazika" (Essays on the word formation of the Persian language), and the Iranian Dr. Iron Kalbosi "Sāxt-e ešteyāyi-ye vāže" (Derivative construction of the word). We consider their functional-semantic features as well as issues of contextual use.

Methods. In this article, the methods of structural analysis, comparative analysis, description, functional analysis, semantic analysis and statistical analysis are used.

Purpose and tasks. The purpose of this article is to study the functional and semantic variants of suffixal allomorphs that form object nouns in the Persian language. To achieve this goal, the following tasks are identified:

1. To study the composition and functional and semantic properties of suffixal allomorphs forming object nouns.
2. To provide scientific conclusions based on the results of the analysis.

Main Part. Uzbek linguists M. Hamroyev, D. Muhammedova and other linguists in their work "Mother Tongue" define object-making affixes as follows: added to the base of the verb, it forms a noun, a weapon, a thing that is the result of an action and a situation or that is used to perform an action. In rare cases, nouns, adjectives, and similes can be used as a basis for forming nouns of objects, weapons, and units of measurement.¹

Iranian linguist Dr. Irān Kalbāsi in his work "*Sāxt-e eštevāyi-ye vāžē*" calls morph as *vāž* and defines it as follows: "The smallest unit of language that has meaning or form is called morph and the grammatical unit of language is used in word formation as units. A morph is a concept with an abstract meaning, its object, that is, its written expression, is called a morpheme (*vāžak*), and its variants (*gunehā-ye vāžak*) are called allomorphs².

Linguist Peysikov L.S. defining the concept of allomorph as alternatives of a lexical morpheme, he explains it as follows: "In order for a morpheme to be an allomorph, they must have a unifying main feature, that is, a common functional-semantic feature. If the commonality of meaning and function lies in one allomorpheme, the rest of the criteria have a relative character and serve as an

¹Hamroyev M., Muhammedova D. and others. "Mother Tongue". T. 2007. – P. 97.

²Doktor Irān Kalbāsi. *Sāxt-e eštevāyi-ye vāže*. (Derivative construction of the word) Tehrān. 1371. – P. 22.

auxiliary function in determining similarity issues. The commonality of meaning and tasks allows combining different allomorphs.

Thus, two or more elements can be allomorphs of the same morpheme if they:
1) have the same meaning and mission; 2) can exchange places in similar devices;
3) have seats that are used only by themselves; 4) have a common and similar appearance, relative phonetic commonality”³.

Summarizing the opinions of the above linguists, we decided to study the functional and stylistic aspects of the suffixal allomorphs that form object nouns in the Persian language, as well as their use in the same context.

1) The suffix **با** [bā] and its suffixal allomorph **وا** [vā] are used to make object nouns. For example:

دوقوا [duvā] - yogurt and rice soup

ریزبا [rizebā] – type of meal

These suffixal allomorphs can be variants of each other in different nouns. For example:

شوربا [šurbā] - شوروا [šurvā] – soup

بعد هم یک دانه کوفته و یک کاسه شوربا برای زن برد⁴.

Then he brought a piece of kufta bread and a bowl of soup for the woman.

کوفته و شوروا یکی از غذاهای سنتی استان کردستان است⁵.

Meatball soup is one of the national dishes of the Kurdistan region.

The suffix **با** [bā] and its suffixal allomorph **وا** [vā] forms a noun in terms of its function. The words formed by these suffixal allomorphs sometimes differ stylistically, that is, words formed from the suffix **با** [bā] are mainly used in artistic and normative style, while words formed from the suffix **وا** [vā] are more is used in zaki style. In some places, they can be used interchangeably. The words شوربا [šurbā] - شوروا [šurvā] are among these.

³Peynikov L.S. Ocherki po slovoobrazovaniju persidskogo yazika. (Essays on word formation of the Persian language). M.: Izdatelstvo MGU, 1973. – P. 29.

⁴iranbanou.com > سرگرمی

⁵<https://ghazaland.com/recipe>

2) The suffix **چه – če** and its suffixal allomorphs **یچه – iče**, **یزه – ize** serve to form object nouns as well as diminutive forms

امبرچه [ambarče] – pendant, medallion.

ماهچه [mohiče] – leg, muscle (human limb)

ماهچه‌های اسکلتی با استخوان‌ها همکاری نزدیکی دارند تا بدن تو را قوی و قدرتمند کنند.⁶

Skeletal muscles work closely with bones to keep your body strong and strong.

طاقچه [tāγče] – shelf

پروانچه [parvānče] – school graduation certificate

چه – če suffix is also used to make words with polysemantic meaning. For example:

تاریخچه [tārixče] – 1) history, 2) history of the question, 3) small story

دریچه [dariče] – window, sunroof

از دریچه به بیرون نگاه می‌کنم مرد قصاب را می‌بینم.⁷

I look out the window and see the butcher.

سرخیچه [sorxiče] – سرخیزه [sorxize] – measles

The suffix **چه – če** and its suffixal allomorphs **یچه – iče**, **یزه – ize** functionally form object nouns. There is no difference in the stylistic use of the suffix **چه – če** and its allomorph **یچه – iče**. These suffixal allomorphs are not interchangeable. Because if the suffix **چه – če** is added to the stem ending with a vowel, its suffix allomorph **-йчиче** is added to the stem ending with a consonant. But the suffix allomorphs of **یچه – iče**, **یزه – ize** can come interchangeably. The words **سرخیچه [sorxiče] – سرخیزه [sorxize]** are among them. In this case, the variant of the suffix **یزه – ize** is considered archaic.

⁶<http://salamati.ir/2016/12/12>

⁷Sādegh Hedāyat. Bufekur. Bambey. 1937. – P. 57.

3) The suffix **مان-*mān*** and its suffixal allomorph **مان-*emān*** were combined with PrTVB and PTVB to form object nouns. These additions are productive suffixes. For example:

ساختمان [*sā.xtemān*] - building

در زندگی شهرنشینی امروزی، با افزایش جمعیت، فشردگی و همجواری بین **ساختمان** ها زیاد شده و ساختمان ها ارتفاع گرفته اند⁸.

*Dar zendegi-ye šahrnešini-ye emruzi, bā afzāyēš-e jamiyat, fešārdegi o hamjavāri beyn-e **sāxtemānhā** ziyād šode va sāxtemānhā ertefāe gerefteand.*

In today's urban life, with the increase in population, the density and proximity between **buildings** has increased, and buildings have become taller.

سازمان [*sā.zemān*] - union

زایمان [*zā.yemān*] - birth, place of birth

Suffixal allomorphs **مان - *mān*** - **مان - *emān*** can be replaced. For example:

دودمان [*dudmān*] / دودمان [*dudemān*] - family

The suffix **مان-*mān*** and its suffixal allomorph **مان-*emān*** functionally make object nouns. Stylistically, nouns formed by both can appear in texts of different styles. Suffixal allomorphs **مان - *mān*** - **مان - *emān*** can be interchanged with each other in artificial nouns. In this case, the suffix **مان - *mān*** is typical of all styles, while the suffix allomorph **مان-*emān*** is typical of the oral style.

Conclusion. Based on the analysis of the sources, it was found that,

1. Object nouns formed with the suffix **با - *bā*** can be found in texts of any stylistic type. Artificial nouns formed with the suffix **وا - *vā*** are mainly characteristic of oral speech. Some spoken words, including artificial nouns such as **دوقوا** [*duvā*], have entered the standard language.

⁸<https://www.chidaneh.com/ideabooks>

2. Nouns formed with the suffix چه – *če* and its allomorphs یچه – *iče* can be found in texts of any stylistic type. The classic variant of the suffix یچه – *iče* is the artificial nouns formed with the suffix یزه – *ize* which can be found in works of art.

3. Object Nouns formed with the suffix مان – *mān* and its suffixal allomorph - مان – *emān* can be found in texts of any stylistic type.

As a general conclusion to the article, it can be said that object-object nouns formed through noun-forming suffixal allomorphs lead to the enrichment of the Persian language vocabulary and the increase of various phonetic and stylistic options.

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